

FutureTDM

Explore . Analyse . Improve

REDUCING BARRIERS AND INCREASING UPTAKE OF TEXT AND DATA MINING FOR RESEARCH ENVIRONMENTS USING A COLLABORATIVE KNOWLEDGE AND OPEN INFORMATION APPROACH

Deliverable D2.2

Stakeholder Involvement Roadmap and Engagement Strategy

Project

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1 SUMMARY

The present use of text and data mining (TDM) in Europe is significantly lower than in the US and parts of Asia¹, and it is important to discern why this is the case. To understand the barriers that inhibit the uptake of TDM we need to speak and listen to stakeholders, the people that contribute to, develop and benefit from content mining. It is therefore a core goal of FutureTDM to **identify** and **engage** stakeholders throughout the course of the project and beyond.

For the purposes of effective stakeholder engagement, this roadmap and strategy will first categorise a number of identifiable groups of stakeholders so that future engagement and communication activities can be tailored to meet their needs. Engagement will also be defined and activities along a general timeline set out, providing a framework for action. More detailed communication targets and dates will be built in to the FutureTDM Communication and Exploitation Plan. In combination, these engagement and communication activities will allow the project to reach and hear from the widest possible range of stakeholders in the field of TDM.

Engagement is a two way process, involving both information dissemination and stakeholder feedback. To do this it is essential that we can communicate the work of the project as clearly and effectively as possible, providing ample opportunity in a variety of forums where stakeholders can comment. It is this continual engagement and empowerment of the stakeholders, as well as close cooperation with related project consortiums that will be critical factors in the success of the FutureTDM project. Finally, the project can only be meaningful if there is sustainable engagement that means setting in motion a longer term process to identify new stakeholders and encouraging existing stakeholders to use their forums to engage further.

¹ http://ec.europa.eu/research/innovation-union/pdf/TDM-report_from_the_expert_group-042014.pdf

2 INTRODUCTION TO FUTURETDM

2.1 Project background and project goal

The exponential growth of data in the digital age has led to the development of powerful techniques for effectively harnessing digital information and discovering new knowledge. In this context, text and data mining (TDM) enables businesses, governments, journalists, researchers etc. to analyse, extract insights and knowledge, and exploit diverse and complex datasets from various digital media. However, the present use of TDM in Europe is significantly lower than in the US and Asia, in part perhaps due to limitations imposed by the European legal framework. In this light, the FutureTDM project identifies and reduces the barriers that inhibit the uptake of TDM within Europe.

FutureTDM will provide critical up-to-date assessments of legal regulations and policies impacting TDM in the EU, and place them in the international research and innovation context. It adopts a bottom-up approach by initiating dialogue between all relevant stakeholders, engaging them via knowledge cafes, workshops and representation on the advisory board to help identify barriers, common solutions and increase awareness of TDM practices and their potential. This combined approach will lead to developing novel policy frameworks and interdisciplinary case driven practitioner guidelines facilitating the spread of TDM activities. Key to success will be the engagement of actors in the broader community (businesses, libraries, publishers, funders, etc.), who will be mobilised through workshops and will be provided with targeted recommendations in the Roadmap for TDM's uptake. The knowledge distilled from quantitative and qualitative research will be integrated into a Collaborative Knowledge Base and Open Information Hub (www.FutureTDM.eu) using insightful visualisations. This dynamic platform will showcase excellence in TDM research and data-driven innovation and serve as reference for current and FutureTDM practitioners ensuring broader TDM uptake to boost Europe's research and innovation capacities.

2.2 WP2 Involve: Stakeholder integration, workshops and advocacy

The very first of FutureTDM's main objectives is to **involve** all key stakeholders via targeted stakeholder consultation to identify practices, requirements, and specific challenges in the field of TDM and installation of an advisory board and integration of practitioner groups in local and pan-European workshops.

The anticipated FutureTDM platform is meant for use not only by developers and researchers, but also a variety of other end-users including publishers, funders, public bodies, research organisations, technology firms, content and data providers and management companies, and many more. As such, the project takes on the ambitious objective of integrating and involving stakeholders from the outset. This continual multi-stakeholder involvement throughout the project gives FutureTDM a unique scope in ensuring that prospective changes to TDM activities in Europe are driven by strategic

engagement and empowerment activities. The consortium partners will define relevant stakeholder groups, and collect potential practitioner groups across different TDM influenced sectors. Through the use of comprehensive stakeholder studies and consultations the project will identify potential early adopters of the FutureTDM platform. These early-adopters will assume critical roles in the functionality, calibration and validation of the collaborative and support information platform. The fact that this project will be running alongside the OpenMinTed project provides unprecedented opportunity to provide valuable insight into the existing state of TDM and the barriers that are limiting uptake. Collaboration with the OpenMinTed project will therefore be a prominent feature of the project.

The engagement of stakeholders within the FutureTDM project will be achieved by:

- Identification and collection of relevant stakeholder groups and networks on multiple regional scales to assess the variable perspectives on TDM issues
- Aligning virtual and physical tools for engagement so as to be as inclusive as possible
- Leveraging the existing connections of the very well-connected, community-grounded consortium to kick-start the involvement of key members in the European TDM research and innovation landscape
- Developing creative engagement roadmaps and strategies with the use of surveys, thematic workshops and knowledge cafes to stimulate participation and foster open dialogue via physical and virtual meetings

2.3 Stakeholder involvement roadmap and engagement strategy

This deliverable explains the process for stakeholder identification and outlines potential areas of engagement and strategies for cross-stakeholder fertilisation. It will inform the design and evaluation of the online stakeholder engagement platform (WP6). It aims to ensure maximum stakeholder awareness, involvement and understanding from the outset of the FutureTDM project. Led by LIBER, it has been developed drawing from the expertise of the whole consortium.

3 STAKEHOLDER IDENTIFICATION

3.1 Definition of 'stakeholder'

Stakeholders for FutureTDM are defined as people, networks or organisations with a direct or indirect knowledge of content mining who are affected by the project and who can contribute to its goals. Stakeholders may be actively engaged in text and data mining directly in their day to day activities, as service providers or developers; or they may have an indirect interest in knowledge discovery, analyse and/or make use of the information gleaned through content mining.

3.2 Stakeholder categories

Drawing from the expertise of the consortium, as a starting point, we have identified several stakeholder categories. These categories will help us to engage with stakeholders in a meaningful way, not least through the organisation of thematic knowledge cafes. This is a flexible model with potential to combine or add categories over the course of the project.

3.3 Stakeholder identification methods and network building

A directory of stakeholders will initially be created in an internal spreadsheet. The stakeholder directory will be based on the identified categories of stakeholders². LIBER will first populate and oversee the directory and invite partners to provide content based on their areas of expertise. This information will be the name of the organisation and a contact email address which is already in the public domain. Usually this will be the head of the organisation (Director) and/or the person responsible for text and data mining. As the project progresses and more contacts are made through the engagement methods, more content will be added. Along the project lifecycle stakeholders involved in the knowledge cafes and workshops will be invited to promote the project to their own networks. They will be informed about how to join the stakeholder directory. In the second half of the project the stakeholder directory will be translated into the online stakeholder map, which new stakeholders can add themselves to. In this way the momentum of stakeholder engagement will be kept up and will be sustainable.

3.4 Ensuring sustainable stakeholder inclusion

For the project results to have any credibility, we need to ensure that we have been inclusive. We can never identify and condense feedback from every single TDM related organisation and individual in the EU but we can provide the opportunity for all types of stakeholder to get involved, making sure that the project is accessible and open to any type of feedback.

² Categories may increase as the project matures

The FutureTDM consortium is a reflection of the variety of stakeholders associated with content mining. We will capitalise on this in using the consortium’s extensive network (including OpenMinTed) reaching out to the stakeholder communities and providing them with the tools to extend further to their own communities. This ripple effect will facilitate a long lasting and broad base of awareness and involvement.

3.5 Types of stakeholder

The project has identified several types of stakeholder that differ in their relation to text and data mining, examples are below:

Stakeholder type	Examples	Relation to TDM
Research community	Researchers and their associated organisations Research councils/Research institutes professional associations, universities, scientific organisations, data scientists	Supply content providers with text and data, further knowledge discovery using mined data
TDM content providers	Publishers, national and university library organisations Repositories, open access facilitators, databases, open access publishers	Holders of content that can be mined. May also offer a service
Consumers of TDM	Government, public sector or industry bodies in for example, energy, financial, health care, information technology, telecommunication, retail sectors	Sectors that look to benefit from knowledge discovery, may form public private partnerships
Funders	Public and private funders of TDM initiatives	Economic drivers for TDM development

Policy shapers	EU institutions and national governments, inter-governmental organisations, public sector bodies, advocacy groups and legal experts	Involved in the development of TDM legislation Influencing TDM policy
Service providers	SMEs, industry, not for profit and/or publically funded: technology experts, data centres, service providers i.e. telecommunications, software applications, storage providers for data, developers	Working with computer software. Improving the service interoperability using TDM, enhance TDM usability
Information aggregators and analysts	Big data analytics providers, data services, journalists, news services, search services	Identifying trends and patterns arising from TDM as their main function
Citizens	Citizen scientists	Individuals with an interest in TDM, both users and providers of content

3.6 Stakeholders needs

We have purposefully avoided attributing ‘stakeholder needs’ to each stakeholder type as the purpose of engagement is to determine their experiences with TDM without any pre-formed notions. This highlights the importance of engagement methodology in the process of getting accurate feedback.

1. Making sure that stakeholders are informed, that there are experts who can answer their questions and that they feel comfortable in providing their opinions.
2. Where engagement is made it is important that we make the most of the opportunity, provide food for thought and pose interesting questions.
3. Providing a forum where stakeholders know that their input is valued.
4. Effectively recording feedback.

This is important not only for stakeholder engagement but for the benefit of the consortium and other work package deliverables.

3.7 Inclusivity

There are clearly a large number of TDM stakeholder organisations and one of the challenges and indeed virtues of the project is to ensure the opportunity for all stakeholder types to engage with the project both online and face to face.

FutureTDM has therefore identified **four stakeholder grouping themes** to facilitate engagement. The next chapter looks in more detail at these groupings and how FutureTDM can best ensure involvement of stakeholders in a way that helps achieve the project objectives.

4 MAKING STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT RELEVANT TO THE PROJECT

In engaging with stakeholders the project will look to answer the question how can we improve uptake of TDM in the EU across all sectors?

To answer this, the FutureTDM project deliverables relate to analysis and solutions relevant to TDM landscape in the following four areas, all of which affect TDM uptake:

1. Legal clarity
2. Economy
3. Technical infrastructure
4. Research environment, practices and services

The visual below aligns the stakeholder categories to each of these areas. Based on this model, at least **four thematic knowledge cafes** will be organised to provide feedback opportunities for all of the identified stakeholder categories in a setting that relates most closely to them. Further information on the knowledge cafes can be found in chapter 6.

FutureTDM acknowledge that these four areas are highly interdependent on each other and many stakeholders could legitimately align to more than one of them. However it is likely that no matter what structure is applied to analysing the issue of TDM this would always be the case.

4.1 Knowledge cafes – four themes

4.2 A space to understand, communicate and collaborate

Our aim is to ensure that each stakeholder category has the opportunity to understand TDM, the goals of FutureTDM and the opportunity to provide feedback and collaborate with others. In the Communications and Exploitation plan, both virtual and physical engagement will be looked at in more detail. Meaningful engagement can be achieved via the following tools, developed over the course of the project based on our feedback from the engagement activities:

ENGAGEMENT	Virtual tools	Physical tools
Stakeholders understand text and data mining	FutureTDM video Social media FutureTDM website Consortium websites	FutureTDM workshops Expert Advisory Board FutureTDM knowledge cafes Partners presenting at events Other project events Fact sheets Journal and conference publications
Stakeholders know about the goals and achievements of the FutureTDM project	FutureTDM Video Social media Powerpoint slides FutureTDM website Consortium websites FutureTDM newsletter Press releases Email lists Project reports	FutureTDM workshops/symposium FutureTDM knowledge cafes Presenting FutureTDM at events Surveys Fact sheets
Stakeholders have the opportunity to feedback their experiences and feel comfortable doing so	Short videos Social media FutureTDM website Consortium websites	FutureTDM workshops/symposium FutureTDM knowledge cafes Surveys

	Data hub Blog space/feedback forum	Networking events Joint project events
Stakeholders have the opportunity to collaborate with each other	Data hub Social media FutureTDM website Consortium websites Contacting consortium partners	FutureTDM workshops/symposium FutureTDM knowledge cafes Networking events Contacting consortium partners Joint project events
Synergies with other related projects, particularly OpenMinTed	Linked website with OpenMinTed, re tweets News/Blogs on project websites Newsletter mentions	Joint events Joint workshops Presentations at each-others events

4.3 Feeling comfortable to feedback

TDM is an area with many legal and technical implications, stakeholders will supply better quality feedback where they know what is expected of them and they are adequately informed about both TDM and the project. FutureTDM aims to create a space where stakeholders feel that their input is valued and any feedback is welcome.

4.4 Feedback at any time

All stakeholders will be able to feedback at any point throughout the project. During the first months we aim at creating a moderated blog space on the project website, and thereafter at a similar pace on the online information hub. While there will be 30 targeted surveys, a survey may also be made available online for anyone to take part in. In this way, individuals interested in TDM who cannot attend an event, still have the chance to provide their opinion. These opportunities will be detailed further in the communications and exploitations plan.

4.5 Partner empowerment

Partners will disseminate information throughout their networks and at events. Each partner will be provided with a dissemination pack, including traditional dissemination materials as well as information on how to access project templates for power points, blog formats etc. Dissemination

materials may also be made available in PDF so that they can be easily printed on site if needed at short notice. Information on the dissemination pack will be detailed in the communications plan.

Where partners attend meetings relating to TDM, they will be asked to provide the consortium with their feedback via the FutureTDM project mailing list (google groups). If the meeting is to promote FutureTDM, partners are asked to provide the coordinators with a short description beforehand that can be uploaded to the events section of the website.

5 ENGAGEMENT EXPLAINED

Engagement is a two way process, where by information is disseminated and stakeholders have a means to respond. The following table outlines the main areas for two way engagement with further explanation of each engagement activity below.

Dissemination activities will be looked at in more detail in the Communications and Exploitations Plan

Info Dissemination (mainly one way engagement) examples:	Info and opportunity to feed back (two way engagement) examples:
Project publications	Information hub –including stakeholder map
Articles and papers in journals, magazines, newspapers	Thematic knowledge cafes
Reports on our activities (e.g. report on stakeholder mobilisation)	Multi stakeholder workshops
FutureTDM leaflet	Symposium
Partner/other project websites	Project website
TDM factsheet	Website blog space
Information about TDM events via the Calendar	Presentations at external events and conferences with Q and A
Presentations on slide share	Surveys
Press releases and interviews	Social media channels of the project and other projects and partners
Website newsletter	Interaction with project partners
Posters, postcards	Other project events
Project video(s)	Short video interviews

In addition, the following materials will be made available to the consortium, to support the communication of key messages to stakeholders:

- Power Point template
- Logos
- Blog guide

6 KNOWLEDGE CAFES, MULTI STAKEHOLDER WORKSHOPS, AND SYMPOSIUM, EXPLAINED

This chapter looks in greater detail at the three types of engagement events to be organised as part of the FutureTDM Project:

1. Knowledge Cafes
2. Multi Stakeholder Workshops
3. FutureTDM Symposium

At every event stage we will draw from the expertise of the consortium partners and the Expert Advisory Board. Moreover, in all our engagement activities we will look to answer the following: Why is TDM uptake in the EU lower than in other countries and what can we do about it?

6.1 FutureTDM knowledge cafe roadshow

In the first half of the project, particular emphasis will be placed on the knowledge cafes.

In this project, a knowledge cafe is defined as an informal opportunity for stakeholders to find out about TDM, the FutureTDM project and its goals and to provide the project with feedback. This is likely to be no longer than a half day event providing food for thought and encouraging interaction between attendees, FutureTDM partners will be in attendance to foster discussion and record findings. It is hoped that with opportunity to move about and meet others over a coffee, participants will feel at ease to provide feedback.

Knowledge cafes, under the responsibility of OK/CM, will be prepared in the first months of the project and will run between month 4 and month 11, with at least four knowledge cafe workshops designed to provide a forum for discussion and feedback. The knowledge cafes will not involve presentations, rather an opportunity for participants to talk to each other. Conversation will be facilitated by questions drawn up by the organisers and these will cover the four identified themes. FutureTDM Partners will be there to facilitate and summarise the conversation.

The knowledge cafe location will aim to maximise both geographical and stakeholder accessibility. They will be held in different countries ensuring that there is at least one knowledge cafe easily reachable for a particular community hub, e.g. at least one more easily accessible for the policy shaping, technical, economic drivers and the research community key representatives. Where possible, they will be attached to existing events so as to facilitate attendance (such as the LIBER 2016 conference).

The knowledge cafes will all follow the same format though may differ in conversation emphasis depending on the audience (technical, policy etc.). At each knowledge cafe, mini video interviews will

be offered where attendees can provide their feedback on camera. Because OpenMinTed are also running some thematic stakeholder workshops, both projects will collaborate to incorporate similar features in their event formats, share their findings and avoid duplication of work. More information on the knowledge cafe format and their planned dates will be held will be made available in the Communications and Exploitation Plan.

In accordance with the thematic groupings, a minimum of four knowledge cafes will be run between January-July 2016 but as the knowledge cafes will follow an established format, it is hoped that further knowledge cafes can be quickly arranged when opportunities for stakeholder engagement arise (for example at stakeholder and other project events).

The purpose of the knowledge cafes is to gather a first wave of feedback from stakeholders. They will be sensitively structured so that one group's opinions won't drown out another's. In some cases there may be discussions about where there are legal grey areas, we need to ensure that stakeholders still feel that they can share their concerns about how they can work in this environment, in order for the project to help bring about legal clarity. Knowledge cafes will be held under "Chatham House Rules." In writing up events, in videos or online, comments will not be attributed to a particular respondent unless we have acquired their permission.

Flow of feedback can be facilitated by provision of information in advance of knowledge cafes and workshops so that participants have enough time to digest the issues involved.

To provide food for thought the project plans to produce:

- At least one video made available on the FutureTDM website explaining the project/TDM
- A link to the video(s) and suggestions for further reading that will be sent to participants ahead of the knowledge cafes so that they are prepared with food for thought ahead of their knowledge cafe

Asking the right questions

TDM is a complex subject matter with technical, economic and legal implications. Part of the challenge will be conveying the project in a manner that is relative and clear. In organising the knowledge cafes we will keep in mind the deliverables from the work packages 3, 4 and 5. Partners from these work packages will be asked to supply the knowledge cafe organisers with relevant questions and suggest speakers. Where relevant, we will also align questions with the OpenMinTed workshops.

6.2 Multi stakeholder workshops

Multi stakeholder workshops in FutureTDM are defined as larger events where participants will be invited to reflect on the project's findings and to help identify specific challenges and requirements for the design and implementation of the FutureTDM framework. These will be more structured

events than the knowledge cafes, with presentations, running for the whole day and will be aimed at all stakeholder groupings.

The first multi stakeholder workshop has been preliminarily scheduled for July 2016 and will be a forum for all of those involved to hear how their input has been collated and what will be done in the next phase of the project. This workshop will focus on barriers to TDM drawing primarily from knowledge cafes, TDM events, legal and economic analysis derived from WP2-4. The second workshop will take place in mid 2017 and will focus on solutions, drawing more from the individual surveys, best practices, collaboration opportunities and policy recommendations arising from WP 4 and WP 5 (see flow chart)

Both of the multi stakeholder workshops are planned to take place in Brussels, where representatives from the EU institutions and advocacy groups will be invited to hear about the project findings and its development. This will also provide a forum of engagement for the policy shaper stakeholder category.

6.3 FutureTDM symposium

ARC will be responsible for the European FutureTDM Symposium as a main networking event inviting affected stakeholders and interest groups.

In this task a symposium will be organised to present the FutureTDM platform and stimulate interest in project findings and recommendations from a wide range of stakeholders identified throughout the project and particularly WP2-4. It will also feature trainer sessions for the workshops designed during task 7.4 to equip stakeholders to use these materials within their own communities. More informal sessions will generate ideas from the wider community for ensuring the long term usability and sustainability of the frameworks and knowledge generated by FutureTDM beyond the duration of the project. The Symposium will be scheduled alongside a larger event with an overlap in interested parties, for example a Research Data Alliance conference or CODATA meeting.

The symposium has been preliminarily set for May 2017 and may be part of a two day event, held alongside the second multi stakeholder workshop.

7 ENGAGEMENT FLOWCHART – HOW FUTURETDM EVENTS FEED INTO PROJECT DEVELOPMENT

- **Knowledge cafes** plus
- **WP 7 Disseminate:** Project Communication, publications, mobilisation, networking
- **WP 3 Assessment** of current studies, publications, legal regulations, policies and barriers, and
- **WP 4 Analyse:** Fields of application, projects, best practices and resources (year 1)

Feed into

Multi stakeholder workshop 1 – barriers and

WP 4 Analyse: Fields of application, projects, best practices and resources (year 2)

Feed into

Multi stakeholder workshop 2 – solutions³

Feed into

WP 5 Elaborate: Legal framework, policy priorities, roadmaps and practitioner guidelines

Feed into

- **WP 6 Collaborative knowledge base,** open information hub, awareness raising
- **Symposium**

³ The workshop may be placed along-side the symposium if the decision is taken to hold the workshop and symposium together.

8 ONLINE ENGAGEMENT VIA THE COLLABORATIVE KNOWLEDGE BASE AND INFORMATION HUB

SYNYO will be responsible for developing the project's main online arena for stakeholder engagement and information dissemination. It will be a stable and flexible FutureTDM platform that will contain an open information repository and collaboration space to empower practitioners with the resources to promote the uptake of TDM in Europe.

The Collaborative Knowledge Base and Open Information Hub will guide TDM stakeholders and users with the appropriate resources, including a moderated blog space where stakeholders can comment on recent TDM news supplied by our partners and guest bloggers. Research efforts from previous WPs will be made available via the FutureTDM platform.

It will promote stakeholder connection through expert navigator and directories. The FutureTDM platform will be a unique European resource to link experts and practitioners across multiple sectors to enhance TDM activities. Here we can publish best practice libraries, practitioner guidelines to increase knowledge transfer and promote the sustainable practice of TDM. Practitioner groups will be able to access all the necessary resources for TDM implementation via the platform.

The website will be made available at www.FutureTDM.eu and will be closely linked to OpenMinted with prominent attention both projects, their goals and blogs.

The platform will be completed in the second year of the project and will be periodically tested based on feedback from stakeholder engagement activities.

Further information about the website will be made available in the Communications and Exploitation plan.

9 ENGAGING ONE TO ONE: SURVEYS AND MINI-INTERVIEWS

OK/CM will be responsible for gathering best practice methodologies and uptake barriers from established TDM practitioners as part of WP4 (analyse). In this task, 30 structured interviews will be conducted with various stakeholders, from these 10 case studies will be selected and form a compendium of best practice (D4.5). Two waves of surveys will run – one in each project year, to ensure that they remain current. They will be made available on the web platform.

Questions will be based on the input from all partners and with their work package goals in mind. They may be made available in the Communications and Exploitations Plan. Technical TDM questions addressed via surveys carried out by OpenMinTed will be absorbed via the shared web space.

In addition to the very structured surveys, all stakeholders will have an opportunity to provide feedback on the FutureTDM website via a blog space on the FutureTDM project website. This will be transferred to the main futurtetdm.eu web once it is live. OpenMinTed blogs will also be made available here. Contributions will be made by project partners, invited guest bloggers and interested stakeholders. They will be moderated by FutureTDM partners.

Finally stakeholders will have an opportunity to provide video feedback at the knowledge cafes and events. Short filmed interviews will form part of a FutureTDM video diary and interested organisation representatives will be invited to give brief sound bites on their perceived TDM barriers and solutions.

In this way, feedback will form part of the collaborative knowledge base and open information hub. It will also be fed into the stakeholder workshops and their associated reports.

10 ENSURING SYNERGIES WITH OTHER PROJECTS

The consortium partners are already directly working in a number of other related projects as outlined in the DoA and will be using their own networks to feed-back on possible areas for collaboration. Additional projects in the field of TDM will be identified by FutureTDM partners and in particular as part of WP4 in analysis of the TDM landscape and in the creation of a projects directory in WP6. Using this knowledge we will devise a projects dissemination strategy to ensure visibility of FutureTDM. Dissemination targets in relation to other projects will be addressed in the FutureTDM Communications and Exploitation Plan.

Engaging with other projects will go further than one way dissemination of FutureTDM information. Where possible, FutureTDM will present at events run by other projects to allow an opportunity for question and answer sessions.

FutureTDM and OpenMinTed

It is vital that FutureTDM and OpenMinTed work in close collaboration with each other. Collaboration will take place in areas that enhance both project goals so not if one project's goal is to the detriment of the other's. Consortium partners UVA, ARC and LIBER are involved in both projects and will help to maintain flow of information.

In addition we will have:

- Two round table discussions scheduled with OpenMinTed – either online or in person
- Collaboration on workshops and knowledge cafes structure
- Shared space on FutureTDM.eu

11 A ROADMAP FOR ENGAGEMENT

The graphic below displays the planning framework for stakeholder engagement in the FutureTDM project. It provides a project overview and broad framework in which the project partners can organise engagement activities where they have responsibility. Further information will be made available in the Communications and Exploitation Plan.

FutureTDM Roadmap

Throughout Project: FutureTDM and consortium websites, newsletters, mailing lists, social media, events, presentations, fact sheets, joint project work

Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	July	Aug
PM1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24

12 MONITORING AND RECORDING FEEDBACK

Engagement is fruitless if the knowledge gleaned is not kept and passed on. Even in the early stages this knowledge will be useful both to the stakeholders and to partners in the consortium in developing their work package deliverables.

How will knowledge be passed on?

Partners will be encouraged to prioritise feeding back from events attended via group email. They will be invited to blog about their findings. Each event organised by FutureTDM will be attended by at least one partner taking notes or, where appropriate, other forms of feedback including straw-polls and visualisations. Other channels for information gathered will include project publications, surveys and videos. FutureTDM event organisers will look into sending post workshop surveys.

Finally there are a number of project deliverable reports which are intended to serve as formal channels of information recording. They include:

- A report on stakeholder mobilisation and perceptions D2.3
- Two reports on multi stakeholder workshops D2.4 and 2.5
- Compendium of best practices and methodologies D4.3

Eventually feedback will be presented as part of the Open Information Hub – a bank of information, intended to be populated for and by stakeholders not least practitioner groups and policy shapers in order to help facilitate uptake of TDM.

13 CONCLUSION

In this document (D2.2), the definition of TDM stakeholders, the process for their identification and means to engage with them have been established. Engagement activities have been set within a broad timeline and four thematic areas to facilitate engagement recognised. In achieving the tasks associated with this deliverable, FutureTDM will work, where possible, with other related projects to achieve its goals and in particular with OpenMinTed. This Stakeholder Involvement Roadmap and Engagement Strategy provide the parameters in which the more detailed Communications and Exploitation Plan (D7.2) will operate. FutureTDM has a bottom-up approach and hearing from stakeholders is a core value. Accordingly, in addressing the issue of TDM uptake in the EU, deliverable D2.2 has a strong emphasis on meaningful stakeholder engagement which is for the benefit of the whole project.